

AI Influence Among Gen Z Employees in Today's Hybrid
and AI-Influenced Work Environments After the Pandemic

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Abstract:

Ever since the pandemic that was COVID in the year 2020, the idea of online-meetings through Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams and other online-meeting apps have shifted from being a supplement to a necessity. With the virus spreading at a rate of 10 million people, and claiming thousands of lives in just the span of a single year, staying indoors entirely, with very little public interaction was more than justifiable (CDC Museum COVID-19 Timeline, 2024). However, in the case of the modern era, it almost seems that the human race, the newer generations have not quite left the world of technology behind. With so many classes that used to be entirely in-person now becoming online or hybrid, there poses a question of how does new AI and technology affect the new generations, and how these individuals have to adapt to these new lifestyles, under new leadership and motivation strategies to get through the day. Despite it only being half a decade, the pandemic is not a period to forget; the world may have forever changed towards the advocacy of AI and technology, for better or for worse.

Link to Research form:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1sqJhV_vfdNWNcr5N986sbsPLfZcRIGvgEO6do1r1jo/edit

Introduction:

The world post-Covid has never quite been documented. In a period where the entirety of the world enters the online realm in order to assimilate or continue their normal activities, it would be considered ignorant to not view the inherent change. With behavioral therapist Reuben Kindred regarding the pandemic as a negative shift in mental health throughout the world, where even video meetings can not capture the true essence of an in-person event (2023). With this apparent factoid, one should peer into the world as it continues to develop, and seemingly

resume as normal. With the prevalence of AI and the hybrid workforce among Gen Z employees, the leadership and motivation strategies may not quite be the same. The traditional office life with a top-down hierarchy may be considered obsolete or undermined under the presence of the use of products like OpenAI to create agendas and guide teams to reach quotas or certain goals.

Body Paragraph 1: How AI and Technology has Developed Throughout the Years

The very notion of AI and technology having a visible, prevalent development on Gen Z is almost exaggerated. According to a study conducted by Illuminas, a radius company that specializes in growth and technology, It was found that Gen Z (1997-2012) are much less enthusiastic about the manufacturing of new "technological breakthroughs." This is likely due to the premise of rapid evolution of technology, going from flip phones to mobile phones in a very limited time frame. As a result of these changes happening at an alarming rate, Gen Z becomes numb to the world of technology around them, despite the clear and very active changes it has on them: from something as simple as calling a cab to writing up a whole paper for an assignment, all without the worry of incoherent handwriting, spelling or loss of resources like paper or ink. On the contrary, the technological change as well as the recognition of is extremely visible when referred to Gen X, or people living within the era of 1965 and 1980 ("Which Generation Loves Technology the Most? You'll Be Surprised at the Answer!," 2024). With the creation of the modern computer happening just a few years prior, and the development of modern phones being far from creation, a Gen X individual experiencing these relatively new smartphones seem to develop a distaste for these products, and are more comfortable with their outdated products, despite these newer innovations possessing a better capability to perform the same tasks. While the concept of a 'resistance to change' is certainly not exclusive to AI growth and technology

development, more often found in fields of management and leadership, the change that is recognized amongst these rapid technological advancements is what drives these anxieties among older generations. Psychotherapist Kealy Spring (2021) notes that often, the fear that is concluded with the resistance of adjustment, comes from an inner fear of the unknown. Perhaps the fear of GEN X is justifiable when one considers how interconnected the world has become. Being able to “friend” someone from across the world or send an email or text to someone hundreds of miles away from you for them to receive it in a split second; creating a new form of interaction that was otherwise found within a dreamscape. This clear distinction of technology irregularity between these two generations acts a catalyst of what's to unfold in much later years. The sudden shift in technology may be considered almost sci-fi from generations like GEN X and onward, but for GEN Z, these changes are almost invisible. Though invisible, these effects are far from changing and may lead to a drastic segmentation of what will happen in later generations, and how GEN Z may be considered an oddity (rather than the aforementioned GEN X) for their generations to come after.

Body Paragraph 2: How Covid-19 has affected the work Environments

Taking place in late 2020, COVID-19 was formally known as SARS-CoV-2, was believed to have emerged among affected individuals in Wuhan China, and has spread across the world fairly quickly over the course of many months after its discovery. China, being an extremely populous country with over 1 billion active residents, the virus spread there considerably fast too. Contrary to western media and belief, the virus was not believed to be spread around the notion of people eating bats, but rather indecent exposure to an animal infected with a similar or the same variant of the virus (Unclassified-Summary-of-Assessment-on-COVID-19-Origins, n.d.). The virus was known to directly attack one’s respiratory system - primarily affecting elderly and

infantile individuals, and it was fortunately found out that a wellness procedure for those to have it was to ingest large quantities of vitamin-C paired with isolation and exercise. When the virus had taken track into the U.S., it initially had led to a small unexpected break for students in schools, which had later led to layoffs of blue collar jobs like bus-driving, and anything that required close proximity of contact. Naturally, this would eventually lead to the mask-mandates, curfew times, six-foot social distancing and required vaccinations, which would also inevitably lead to protests. Protests by teachers in schools specifically, against the required vaccinations would require immediate dismissal of their jobs, regardless of one's tenured status or not (Will, 2020). Though the shift was alleviated with the aid of online schools through platforms like Google Classroom, Zoom, and unemployment checks and food aid, the entirety of COVID had developed a lasting impact on growing adults and children alike (Will 2020). According to the national institute of mental health, the lockdowns associated with COVID and the less than genuine online interactions that have occurred to supplement against the once prevalent in-person associations have been linked to anxiety, depression, and even substance abuse disorder. An alluding phenomenon that many individuals have developed was a condition known as "LONG COVID" a condition that induced neurological symptoms such as difficulty concentrating, sleep, as well as the aforementioned depression and anxiety (*COVID-19 and Mental Health*, n.d.). Social scientist Thomas Roulet (2025) links such concerns with modern day AI application that an individual who has experienced COVID may have their jobs impacted. He had found out the use of artificial intelligence is often considered too reliant, mimicking human abilities at the cost of putting workers' health at risk. Additionally, in a work setting, those who tend to use AI more than others have "eroded" their traditional ways of collaborating. This suggests the notion that AI is not being used as a supplement in these work

settings; making employees develop an over-attachment to AI and miss out on necessary human interaction and collaboration post-COVID (Roulet, 2025). A study among students in the College of Staten Island however, seems to combat this singular notion.

Body Paragraph 3: Sample Study of GEN Z Employees and AI.

With the aid of Dr. Jong Gyu Park, a google form was sent out to multiple, student-led powerful organizations present at CSI. These include, but are not limited to CSI's student government - an organization that focuses on the well-being of students and activities through the use of the student activity fees, and CSI's own ALFPA (Association of Latino Professionals for America) organization. In the form the following questions were asked: "How would you generally describe yourself socially before COVID?", "How would you generally describe yourself socially after COVID?" "When the mask mandate was announced, and there was a period where everyone was wearing masks, how did you feel about it?", "Would you agree that COVID-19 has most likely hindered social growth towards everyone collectively?", and lastly, "As a current employee in the workplace, how have you feel AI has impacted your workstyle, leadership, and motivations?" With a sample size of thirty anonymous students on campus, the pie chart shown in figure 1¹ suggests that there is almost an equal mix of social types before COVID-19. The chart shows that the least percentage of people considered themselves ambiverts - individuals who considered themselves expressing traits of intro and extraversion, 33.3% for those who were extroverts - people who consider themselves social in any and all situations, and a whopping 36.7% for those who have considered themselves introverts, or not social in any and all situations. However, upon viewing figure 2² we notice a considerable change in the chart with

¹ How would one generally describe themselves before the COVID-19 Pandemic.

² How would one generally describe themselves after COVID-19 Pandemic.

the lowest description people describe themselves as now being extroverts at 26.7%, followed by introverts at 33.3%, and ambiverts at a whopping 40%. This sudden decrease in extroverts followed by ambiverts taking the lead majority may signify well with the complications that may occur as a result of people staying in constantly, with the only outlet to the real world being their device(s). It also may imply how socially impaired an individual may have been over time due to the lack of social interaction they may have once had at their job, school, and or other leadership based activities they may have been involved in. Additionally, With the other previously mentioned responses we found out that introverts were more in favor of the anonymity that the mask mandates provided, agreed that COVID generally hindered their social growth, and found that there was just too much of a reliance on AI, despite it being a powerful tool if used correctly. Ambiverts on the other hand, felt that mask-mandate was "necessary" despite the mental tolls that came with it. They also commented how social growth was definitely impeded due to COVID, but allowed for more forms of self-expression (i.e. through masks and online sharing) that would not have been possible without the pandemic. However, when asked about AI's workplace impact, they felt that it hindered the work of traditional skills and that its efficiency did not outweigh their fears of eventual overreliance on AI. Lastly, the extroverts disliked the mask mandates, often finding it to be isolating and restrictive, and even embarking how COVID as a whole put a stump in both their mental and social growth. However, dissimilarly to the introverts and ambiverts, they viewed the AI's workplace impact to be generally positive, seen as a tool to aid in one's growth and productivity; despite underlying fears to adapt to a more "tech-based environment."

How would you generally describe yourself socially before COVID?

30 responses

Image of how students with a sample size of thirty CSI view themselves socially *before* COVID.

How would you generally describe yourself socially after COVID?

30 responses

Image of how students with a sample size of thirty CSI view themselves socially *after* COVID.

Concluding Statements and Constraints:

To conclude, COVID-19, above all else, was a unique experience to everyone. The shift to online, the fear of uncertainty, the overwhelming use of electronics just to carry out a typical day pre-COVID, all of these experiences were quite drastic. To say that AI did not flourish or

kickstart off dramatically during this era would be considered an understatement. The use of AI among students has become significantly prevalent in both schools and the workplace. While the study conducted does show some constraints, such as its small sample size of thirty participants, as well as having too many open-ended questions that lead to interpretation and summation via open-ended responses rather than a continuity of multiple-choice results, one may argue with, due to the nature of the sample size, the individualized responses helped propel the notion forward that the AI is undoubtedly a powerful tool, no matter the location or place it is used in. However, it should be used in moderation, and as a supplement; the threats AI may pose to one's work, job, and or livelihood are grand if left unchecked. So efforts should be made in schools and organizations to keep such an ever expanding tool at ease for now and for future generations to come.

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